

econology

May 2026 | Issue 05

'May day! May day!'

Bangladesh's smoking crisis

Life on water locked climate frontline

The unsung heroes of circular economy

Coal & China's green transition

UP IN SMOKE

<https://theconology.com/>

econology

The team at a glance

Editorial Advisor

Jishan Ara Mitu

Editor-in-chief

Shakil Khan

Editorial Director

Julfekar Dehan

Creative Editor

Mahdi Hasan

Communications Lead

Tanvir Ahmmed

Growth & Tech Lead

Rashedul Hasan

External Relations Lead

Nahid Islam

External Relations Associate

Nahid Khan Niloy

External Relations Associate

Fariha Tabassum

Research Wing

Nasif Anam

Tasnuva Tanzum

Naomi Rahman

Mousumi Sweety

Contents

In-depth

Behavioral cues, tax tiers and silent mechanism behind Bangladesh's smoking crisis..... 4

Timeline

'May day!, May day'.....8

Analysis

Comparative development trajectories Singapore and Bangladesh....30

Rethinking refugee governance in South Asia.....50

Policywatch

The unsung heroes of circular economy.....18

Feature

The uncounted journey: life on water locked climate frontline.....12

Energy

Coal in the shadows of China's Green Transition20

Workers at Crossroads: Labour and the Politics of Nigeria's Energy Transition.....26

Opinion

Procedural Efficiency and the Green Transition....33

The Silent Revolution ...45

Incentives & Environmental Literacy in Society... 41

AI integrated drug research by Ghanaian Scientist... 38

Reflections

You vs You: The Conflict Between Your Condition and Your Choice.....36

Cover Background

The cover is a stylized version of the kinetic art "You'll Never Smoke Alone Again" by Jakob Grosse-Ophoff. Its usage is intended to portray the repetitive and almost mechanical mindset of the smoker.

A habit state can't quit

Behavioral cues, tax tiers, and silent machinery behind Bangladesh's smoking crisis

Mahdi Hasan & Shakil Khan

Illustration: Mahdi /Econology/

Cigarettes function as euphoric pleasure enhancers, contain neurotropic compounds that boost brain activity, all whilst slowly eating away the life of the smoker with each puff. The diverse, unpredictable behavioural pattern from smokers, triggered by a wide range of seemingly innocent visual cues often casts a huge question mark on the whole point of government-imposed paternalist schemes, especially in developing countries like Bangladesh, where the taxation scheme is mostly archaic.

The hyperfixation on increasing tobacco prices rarely addresses phenomena like downward substitutions or how a gradual increase of taxes can subdue rising health costs.

The Tobacco situation in Bangladesh

Almost 35.3% adults in Bangladesh are addicted to tobacco, among which 18% are addicted to cigarettes, and 20.6% are addicted to SLT (World Health Organisation). Cigarette smoking is still the sole cause of 22% of the total deaths in the country. Though the prevalence of smoking has dropped across the country as a result of years of taxation, there is a huge percentage of smokers who behave inelastically to tax imposition, despite not having high incomes.

This phenomenon can be described as inelastic in terms of unaffected cigarette consumption, and elastic in terms of

downward product substitution, from high-tier/mid-tier brands to low-tier brands (Nigar Nargis et al., 2019)

Another paper shows how low-tier cigarettes have increased their market revenue by almost 40%, from FY 2006-07 to FY 2017-18 (Ahmad, Hossain, et al., 2019). When it comes to smokeless tobacco [SLT] use, Bangladesh ranks second (next to India) among 34 high SLT burden countries (Sinha and Yadav, 2017, S Mitra, 2024). Unlike cigarettes, smokeless tobacco (jorda) has much less proportional reduction in consumption due to price increase.

Bangladesh’s tobacco taxation scheme

The taxation scheme can be defined as a multi-tiered ad valorem taxation. In the 90’s, the country was still operating on the British Colonial excise system, strictly focusing on revenue generation as a fiscal tool. When the VAT Act of 1991 was introduced, the tobacco products were bought under Ad Valorem, which meant tax could be charged as a percentage of the price of a good, i.e. a fixed percentage was imposed on the transaction value of cigarettes. Then, around 2005, the Tobacco Control Law formalised a ‘multi-tier tax

structure’ which enabled different ad valorem rates for different tiers of cigarettes (e.g. low, medium, high, premium).

One of the core problems of the multi-tiered ad valorem is that it enables downward substitution of tobacco products, hence the revenue shares of low-tiered cigarettes continued despite the persistence of taxation. As critiques of the existing multi-tiered tax system grew, the government had to make some minor adjustments, such as increasing floor prices for lower-tier cigarettes.

However, the predominant multi-tiered structure continued to persist, despite the narrowing of price gaps. The critics continued to raise their voice for a specific excise tax that would take into consideration the public health issue and would ‘indiscriminately’ raise prices for all types of cigarettes. But is the imposition of a specific excise tax really a sustainable corrective tax policy for Bangladesh? Would it be really different from the colonial excise system, despite theoretical consideration of internalising negative externality?

Bangladesh continues to retain colonial characteristics by pooling tax revenues with other fiscal revenues within the general

Item	Year(s) covered	Level (BDT billion, approx.)	Implied average annual increase over interval	Notes
Cigarette tax revenue (SD+VAT)	2011–12 to 2017–18	From earlier lower base to 228.1 in 2017–18	≈ 11% real per year (cigarette tax revenue only)	Estimated real growth rate of cigarette tax revenue over FY 2011–12 to 2017–18 from detailed tax study. (Sources: economicsforhealth)
Projected total tobacco tax revenue (all products, SD+VAT+HDS)	2023–24 to 2024–25	From ≈ 37.0–37.5 thousand crore to 47.4 thousand crore	≈ 28% nominal increase in one year	2024–25 tax proposal projects an extra BDT 10.4 thousand crore over previous fiscal year. (Sources: bnpp)
Total economic cost of tobacco (smoked only)	2004 to 2017–18	From an earlier 2004 estimate (noted as “more than doubled” to 305.6 in 2017–18)	≈ 4–5% real per year (order-of-magnitude)	2018 study notes total economic cost in 2017–18 was BDT 305.6 billion and had “more than doubled” since 2004. (Sources: cancer+1)
Direct healthcare costs attributable to tobacco	2017–18	83.9	– (single benchmark)	Tobacco-attributable direct healthcare costs; about 9% of government health expenditure that year. (Sources: tobaccotas+1)
Total economic cost of tobacco (all smoked and smokeless; health + productivity)	2017–18	305.6	– baseline	National cost-of-illness estimate for 2017–18 (1.4% of GDP). (Sources: cancer+1)
Total economic cost of tobacco (updated; includes health + productivity + environment)	2018 to 2024	From 305.6 (2017–18 baseline) to 875.44 in 2024	≈ 18–19% nominal per year	Updated 2024 study finds total annual economic cost reaches 875.44 billion (1.58% of GDP), almost 3× the 2018 level. (Sources: economicsforhealth+1)
Health-related economic cost of tobacco (healthcare + morbidity and mortality)	2024	730.63	– (single benchmark)	Of the 875.44 total, 730.63 billion (83.5%) are health-related costs; 307.71 billion are direct health expenditures. (Sources: economicsforhealth+1)

consolidated fund. Even if the government imposes specific excise taxes, the hoped outcome will unlikely be achieved due to the absence of a defined compensatory allocation towards health expenditures.

Behavioural economics of tobacco addiction

A study was conducted around 2012 by John Acker and James MacKillop concerning the subjective craving of tobacco users from diverse racial backgrounds in a controlled cue-elicited virtual reality environment. The subjective dimension of cravings and the demand indices (Omax, Breakpoint, elasticity) were calculated using a robust mixture of Nonlinear Exponential curve model, ANOVAs and hierarchical regression. For ease of interpretation, the inverse value $[1/\alpha]$ was calculated for elasticity, where greater alpha values indicate greater price insensitivity.

The repeated measuring of ANOVA revealed statistically significant increases in several indices of demand and craving.

Significant increases were observed in the demand indices of elasticity, O max, and Breakpoint, pointing to the presentation of tobacco cues resulting in higher price insensitivity for cigarettes, as well as greater maximum expenditure for cigarettes and willingness to pay for cigarettes at higher prices. Another interesting insight was that ‘income’ was not significantly associated with the demand indices.

Though the study was conducted outside Bangladesh, it still gives us a glimpse of the complex nature of human behaviour. In a time of rapid technological advancement, such rigorous studies ought to be conducted in the context of developing countries like Bangladesh, where the policy makers are still hyperfixated on income level and price increase of Tobacco products.

But what about the tobacco industry? It appears that they are two steps ahead of the government, and they are highly familiar with the power of visual cues and integrate them within their marketing agenda, without falling into any of the nullifiers

of existing anti-tobacco laws. The tobacco companies utilise visual cues, such as seemingly innocent hangout sessions with friends or sipping chai by the roadsides, coupling them with brand-specific colours to integrate a distinct ‘dog-whistling’ strategy to promote their product. Such subtle strategies easily bypass the existing archaic loopholes of government-imposed censorship.

Policy suggestions

Coupling the tobacco tax revenue with healthcare costs (i.e. earmarking) and using the revenue to challenge the ever-evolving tobacco industry can be one of the basic fixes. As well as ensuring transparency within the NBR.

But they are probably not enough to cure the undying love for cancer sticks that pushes men through all the upheavals and downfalls of life, and accompanies them to the grave.

About authors

Shakil Khan is a young economist who recently completed his undergraduate studies in Environmental Economics. His academic and research interests revolve around sustainability, climate policy, and environmental governance. He aims to pursue further studies and research in Climate Finance to contribute to global climate solutions and sustainable development.

Mahdi Hasan is an undergraduate student pursuing a degree in the Environmental & Resource Economics programme at the Dhaka School of Economics. Apart from his field of study, he also has a passion for the liberal arts and loves to marvel at the complexities of the geopolitical arena.

*He can be reached at:
mahdihasanadib001@gmail.com*

'May Day! May Day!'

140th International Workers' day

Nasif Anam

Soviet Art work titled 'May 1' by Yakov Guminer

During the 1880s, capitalism in the United States was brutal. Workers were required to work from 12 hours up to 16 hours a day, no holiday, seven days a week, under inhumane conditions that degraded the physical and mental conditions of the workers, with no minimum wage or safety regulations. If anyone dared to speak against, was simply discarded and replaced by the endless reserve army of laborers.

In 1884, when a federation of unions passed a resolution, demanding aspects to improve the working environment with 8 hours of working per day, better working conditions, equal pay for women, no wage cuts, and more by May 1st, 1886. But the owners refused. Culminating in strikes throughout the whole country on May 1st, 1886. A massive rally followed in Chicago, the industrial heartland. Slogan rang – “Eight hours for work, eight hours for sleep, and eight hours for what we will!”

The state responded with violence. As a result, the protest intensified. On May 3, police killed four. In response, workers

gathered in Haymarket Square to protest. The protest was going peacefully. There, a bomb by an agent for provocation, killing police officers. The response – the state used a murderous crackdown. Eight workers were framed and hanged following the event, which was sabotaged by the state for the owning class's wish to crush the movement. Proving the role of the state as an instrument of exploitation.

Those eight's execution became the foundational act of the Mayday. In 1889, the Paris International Socialist Congress established the event of May 1st as International Workers' Day, a day celebrating international workers' solidarity in memory of the martyrs of 1886. 140 years have passed since the Haymarket Square event. From pressure, on the surface level, all the demands were fulfilled long ago. But, at the field level, issues remain in one way or another.

In the modern world of globalization, Bangladesh is one of the important economies maintaining the global value chain. Supplying the chain with cheap labor. This status is maintained through the breach of the demands for which the blood was shed in 1886.

To this day, low wages and unsafe working conditions plague. During the Rana Plaza tragedy, the inhumane treatment of the workers in the workplace became clear. Even though various reforms have been taken since. Giant capitals still need those cost-cutting measures to maintain the profit margin. Thus, new ways to exploit come to light fast, too. 32% of the adult garment workers are paid less than the

poverty line of \$2.15 per day. The women's equal pay is still in question. The RMG sector is dominated by female workers. But they provide an opportunity to the owning class to pay less in the name of physical difference or productivity compared to a male worker, despite working the same time and with the same productivity. Making them instrumental for keeping the wage low and profit margin high.

Child labor is still a common view, often in dangerous conditions and physical abuse. Job insecurity and the rise of the informal sectors are also serving as tools for keeping wages low. The movements or strikes for better conditions and wage rises also met with violence from the law enforcement, proving their role in the exploitation again, in fear of losing their place in the global value chain and the revenue generated from the exploitation.

On a global scale, too, Bangladesh is not alone. Other lower-income countries are also experiencing the same in their attempt to maintain the global value chain. The unfair pay, lower wages, unsuitable working conditions, and child labor are still rampant.

In neighboring countries of India, Pakistan, and Nepal. Similar situations are present. Trade wars, illegal wars, and instability are also other factors contributing to the threatening of the livelihoods and imposing socio-economic insecurity. All of these are contributing to intensifying the exploitation even more. As if the 1886 Haymarket affair never happened. This year marks the 140th anniversary of the event in Chicago, celebrating the international

workers' solidarity, celebrating the sacrifice made by the martyrs of the event who gave their lives for a better life for the working class – a life with dignity and prosperity, a life as a human, a life without exploitation and violence.

About Author

Nasif Anam is currently studying Development Economics (undergrad) at Dhaka School of Economics. He has diverse interests stretching from philosophy, history to contemporary Economic thought.

He can be reached at: nasifanam@gmail.com

Partnerships at **econ**ology

Structured media partnerships for sustained visibility and engagement

Be a part of the
Young Environmental Economics intelligentsia

3 month integrated Partnership model

- Presence** — Brand introduction & visibility
- Participation** — Events, content, interaction
- Collaboration** — Ongoing involvement & integration

Media Presence

- Magazine features
- Digital visibility
- Co-branded posts

Content Collaboration

- Articles
- Interviews
- Thought pieces

Event Integration

- Media/Knowledge partner
- Seminar & webinar branding
- Event promotion

Audience Access

- Niche academic audience
- Students & Researchers
- Policy-focused readers

Analyzing the environmental woes of the Global South

For partnership inquiries and detailed proposals, please contact

+8801560-054-456

hq.econology@gmail.com

[company/theconology](https://www.linkedin.com/company/theconology)

Grow with an emerging academic platform

The uncounted journey: Life on water locked climate

| *Shakib Alam Prithul*

| *Fundraising Officer, Research and Advocacy Cell, Shushilan*

Pic: clicked by the author

“Floods and erosion have swallowed our land more times than I can count. Every home we build is temporary. Every field we plant may vanish overnight. It feels like we don’t belong here.” - Rahim (38)

This is not a metaphor for Rahim Mia (38). It is the measure of his life. Once lived with his wife Asma (32) and three children in Lalganj Union of Mehendiganj Upazila, every monsoon brought upheaval. Floods did not come once or twice. They came steadily, eroding their homestead, disrupting their work as fishers and farmers, and erasing the fragile stability they tried to build.

Over the last ten years, Rahim’s family was displaced repeatedly, alone within Mehendiganj. At least 8 times, each time losing place to live, savings, health, memories and the documents that proved

they once had land. In this char landscape, formed and reformed by the currents of the Meghna River and its tributaries, erosion is not an occasional shock. It is an almost predictable hazard. The upazila covers roughly 435.79 sq km, and every year monsoon inundation expands the river’s reach, consuming housing, school yards, roads, mosques, ponds and fields.

Leaves tens of thousands of people dispossessed. Around 9,480 people from more than 1,300 families in the area have already become homeless due to river erosion, but such figures are only the visible layer of harm. When

Home Is Gone, Memories and Security Follow Displacement has meant repeated beginnings for a lot of families in Mehendiganj.

Each time Rahim's home was lost to the riverbank, they had to rent land, borrow money for construction materials, and start again from the beginning. The cyclical nature of this displacement has stripped them of permanence.

Their land deed that once anchored their identity, disappeared in one of these episodes of river encroachment. Rahim's claim to stable shelter and legal belonging vanished with it.

Asma lost the modest buffer they had for hard times, all her jewellery. Their children lost schoolbooks, certificates, and photo albums documenting their family's stories. In these losses, the family's history was rendered invisible.

"Sometimes it feels like we are vagabonds, not by choice, but by force." - Rahim (38)

This is not occasional adversity. It is cumulative. What erosion takes is not only physical land but also continuity, memory, and future potential. The losses that cannot be quantified in monetary values.

In areas like Ulania, lalganj and Kaliganj, displacement has become routine impacts of climate change. Communities rebuild again and again, but the sense of stability never returns. Each forced relocation fractures social bonds and erodes

psychological resilience. Which cannot be captured but the statistics on hectares lost.

Debt and daily survival

Rahim's core skill has always been fishing. But repeated displacement fractures even that identity. Each relocation demands new home, new networks, new mooring places, and new agreements with local mohajon.

To rebuild home, secure nets, boats, and gear, fishermen like Rahim enter into dadon money lending system, a form of cyclical loan dependency that is practically impossible to break. In lean months, incomes fall. During floods, fishing is also near impossible. With each episode of economic stagnation, debt climbs. Instead of accumulating savings or thinking of quality life and nutrition, the family is locked in survival cycles.

"Sometimes it feels like we are vagabonds, not by choice, but by force"

"There are days when we have to choose between food, medicine, and safety."

Rahim (38)

The highcost of emergency health

Healthcare is another front where geography and climate collide with insecurity. The local upazila health complex manages only routine care. For serious health issues like complicated pregnancies, injuries, or infections, the families must cross the river to Barishal Medical College Hospital. There is also no regulated emergency medical boat service in Mehendiganj. During high

water, the public steamer stops. Private speedboats charge exorbitant fares which is also risky. A lack of subsidised transport turns life threatening episodes into financial gambles where delay can mean tragedy. In this context, everyday health risks become climate risks and even life risk.

Children bearing the burden of climate

“When the school was inaccessible, our children’s future became fragile.” -Asma

The economic losses of erosion are recorded in local government assessments. Buildings, land, roads. But the non economic and social dimensions are rarely logged. When schools collapse into the riverbank or the school yard gets submerged under water, attendance drops.

Children like Rahim’s children, who managed to complete high school, find their educational aspirations strained by distance and constant mobility. The distance from their village to Patarhat College, cost them extra money, time and risk as the roads and transportation ways faces challenges too in

the time of disasters. Their daughters enter adolescence navigating puberty without adequate menstrual hygiene products, reproductive health services, or safe school environments, conditions that are direct hit to their basic rights and compound vulnerability. The children says, ‘we face disruption from our education almost every year in monsoon. Sometimes the break is so long that we lose interest.

A lot of our friends have already dropped out due to the struggles and financial instability, some of the girls got married at an early stage too.’ Every disrupted school year, every missed health checkup, and every delay in accessing services becomes another way that climate exposure entrenches inequality. This inequality makes them vulnerable in a structural way that will affect the children in future.

Survival, community, and determination in mehendiganj

“We keep going because stopping is not an option. We cannot give up trying after looking at our children eyes, their spirit of

survival inspires us” says, Asma.

And yet, amid this relentless repetition of loss, the family endures. Neighbours share food. Women in the settlement help prepare meals to the families like Asma’s when a flood overwhelms one household. Asma supports her household using her social network for meals when they don’t have any food even for her children. Rahim gathers early in the morning to salvage wood or rebuild walls before the next tide arrives. This is resilience shaped by necessity, not choice. A practical endurance born of scarcity and insecurity.

Asma’s voice carries both fatigue and fierce determination: “We have been displaced so many times that we do not know what home truly means anymore, but we will not stop trying for our children.” Their survival is not a story of triumph over nature. But of persistence alongside it.

The human cost of erosion

“Every flood takes more than land or crops, it takes schooling for our children, memories we were attached to, and the dignity of having a home. Life feels alienated and fragile at the same time.” Says, Rahim. What Rahim’s family has experienced illustrates a broader truth about climate vulnerability in chars, losses are often invisible to conventional measurement. Government reports may list land lost or houses destroyed but rarely count the children who stop attending school because the nearest one is submerged into water.

They do not account for women who suffers form sexual health. Who skips prenatal visits because transport is unavailable during flood. They do not include the psychological toll of rebuilding

a home eight times, or the way repeated displacement undermines confidence, belonging, and hope. They do not also include the memories lost and trauma occurred due to the disasters.

“Despite everything, we keep rebuilding. Every loss teaches us how to survive a little better, to protect our children a little more, and to hope again for tomorrow.” Says Rahim. Repeated displacement has fractured Rahim’s family, limiting their access to education, health, and economic stability.

It has broken them into pieces and tested their ability to secure even the basic right to a quality life. But each time they start over, they rise with experience, endurance, and a sharper sense of what survival demands. Their lived resilience is not abstract. It is rooted in the daily labour of rebuilding, the collective solidarity of neighbours, social networks, and an unwavering commitment to provide for their children despite structural barriers.

Their story shows that climate vulnerability is not just about extreme events. It is about basic life being disrupted, opportunities deferred, and potential constrained by repeated relocation. It is about how the basic rights to education, health, stability, and dignity are eroded alongside the riverbanks they once called home.

Understanding climate loss and damage through Rahim’s life means recognising that survival is not enough. Policies must address both economic and non economic losses and damages. Only then can resilience be more than endurance. Only then can a family who has survived uncounted loss be seen, counted, and included in solutions that match the scale of their reality.

About the Interviewee

Rahim Mia, a 38 year old fisherman from Mehendiganj Upazila in Barisal Division, Bangladesh, embodies the daily inequities of climate vulnerability in riverine char communities. Repeated riverbank erosion, floods, and cyclones have trapped him and his family in cycles of displacement, loss, and debt. Each season brings the threat of losing their home, belongings, and livelihood. His experience reveals how families in Mehendiganj face irreversible, unrecognised damage from climate change, losses that extend far beyond land to education, health, dignity, and opportunity.

The unsung heroes of circular economy and sustainability in Bangladesh

| *Zobayer Ahmed, Associate Professor (BIGM)*

| *Md. Sahadat Hosain, Dept of Dev Studies, CU*

The informal waste pickers, a group of unsung heroes of Bangladesh, toil tirelessly amidst the chaos of urban life to keep our cities clean and play a crucial yet underappreciated role in the country's waste management system. Despite playing a vital role in the circular economy — a model that emphasizes the recycling and reuse of resources to achieve sustainability goals — they are yet marginalized, facing social stigma, health risks, and deprived of formal recognition in society.

According to a recent study, there are 400,000 waste pickers in Bangladesh. In Dhaka alone, approximately 120,000 to 150,000 informal waste pickers are involved in the recycling trade chain. Around 15%-20% of the total generated solid waste in Dhaka is recycled mainly by informal waste pickers. If Bangladesh is to achieve environmental

sustainability and economic growth in support of the SDGs, the country should recognize and formalize the informal waste pickers who provide essential services at a severe health risk. The circular economy, a more sustainable alternative approach to the conventional linear economy of 'make, take and dispose', is gaining global interest. It focuses on using resources for as long as possible, recovering and reusing materials, which reduces waste and improves resource efficiency.

By diverting waste from landfills and reducing the demand for new raw materials, informal waste pickers play a central role in Bangladesh's recycling system. They are constantly working, collecting, sorting and selling recyclable materials to recover tons of plastic waste that could otherwise become a source of environmental

pollution. The informal recycling industry alone generates BDT 10-15 billion (USD 100-150 million) in business a year in Dhaka city only. It will not only reduce environmental pollution but also create a more sustainable economy. Without protective gear, their job puts them at risk of health problems, as sharp objects or harmful chemicals often injure them. However, this is exacerbated by poor access to health care, leading to recurrent infections and chronic diseases.

To secure and manage their basic needs, these informal waste pickers toil relentlessly.

Trapped in a vicious cycle of poverty, their sense of well-being is further eroded by limited job security, the absence of social protection, and minimal access to financial services, all of which prevent them from improving their lives or investing in their children's education. To make matters worse, the social stigma attached to their work marginalizes them, diminishing their sense of self-worth and making it harder for them to demand fair wages or recognition for their invaluable contributions. Despite their crucial role in recycling, informal waste pickers in Bangladesh are not focused yet by the interim government.

Formalizing and empowering their work can go a long way to achieve four key Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): SDG 1 (No Poverty), SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities) and SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities). To lay the groundwork for a more equitable and sustainable future of the country, the interim cabinet should work effectively to uplift this group. Integrating informal waste pickers into the circular economy requires

a number of important policy actions. Waste pickers need to be recognized as essential workers who require legal protections and better working conditions. Healthcare, education, and social protection would have the additional benefit of improving their well-being and empowering them to invest in their future. Training programs can support their skills and earning potential, while public awareness campaigns can combat the stigma they experience. Hence, formally acknowledging their roles in waste management systems will end the endless cycle of waste picking in exchange for a safer, stable job, as well as pursuing the efficiency of waste management systems, leading to an easier and sustainable world.

Acknowledging them is not just a social justice issue — supporting waste pickers with their settlement is actually a smart investment in a fairer, more inclusive and sustainable economy. As Bangladesh becomes more and more urban, its importance will only rise. We need to invest in them because they are vital for a sustainable future. Therefore, it is critical to create more collaborative strategies between the government, non-government organisations (NGOs) and the private sector to support waste pickers across the country in meeting the immediate needs of the unsung heroes of sustainability. Access to regulated labor, healthcare, education and integration into formal waste management systems for the heroes will lead to a more inclusive economy where everyone can thrive.

Coal in the shadows of China's green transition

Nasif Anam

A managed strain beneath stability

In early August 2024, the megacity of Hangzhou, home to over 12 million people, banned all non-essential outdoor lighting and light shows. This happened in the summertime, when heatwaves were present and energy-consuming electronics like air-conditioning systems were operating, and it still shows an issue beneath the surface faced by the world's second-largest economy (according to the nominal GDP measure): a struggle to keep up with rapidly growing energy demand.

Being the country with the world's second-largest population, China has been a pioneer of renewable energy expansion, as this country has added 430 million kWh of

renewable energy (in the form of solar and wind) in 2025 alone. Yet, during extreme climates such as heatwaves, these energy sources often become less reliable to meet the supply requirement of over 10 trillion kWh. So, to stabilize the supply, authorities are continuously expanding coal and other non-renewable sources of power. Thus, the non-renewable sources remain an important stabilizer.

Rising demand: The structural driver of energy pressure

This problem is rooted in the increase in energy demand over the supply. As of 2024, the annual electricity consumption growth of the country was 6.1%, while the GDP growth was 5%. This implies that

Illustration: Tanvir/Econology/

the electricity consumption is rising faster than the economy. Thus, China's economic growth is becoming more energy-intensive.

Along with existing traditional energy-intensive industries like steel, cement, glass, chemicals, etc., the growth of electric vehicle usage and AI datacenters is driving the demand higher. While being already home to leading companies of semiconductor, computer, telecom, software, and other IT-based industries.

National Energy Administration (NEA) reported that electric vehicle charging and battery swapping surged over 48.8%, while the electricity required for new vehicle manufacturing increased over 20%. Within IT-related sectors (including data centers, cloud computing, and AI infrastructure) grew 17%. All of these are already surging the energy demand high. The occasional climate-related events (like

heatwaves) are driving up the usage of power-intensive electronic appliances like air-conditioning systems. In the summer of 2025, for example, during record-breaking heatwaves, demand rose to 1.5 billion kW, where ACs and refrigeration accounted for approximately 90% of the incremental load.

Friction between renewable and non-renewable

While responding to the ever-growing hunger for energy, the supply side is comparatively lagging due to distributive and administrative bottlenecks. Though renewable energy capacity has increased drastically. In 2025 alone, wind and solar-based energy production capacity rose to 430 GW, accounting for over 47% of total national capacity. Overall, non-fossil fuel-based energy sources increased to 1494 GW, exceeding 60% of the total installed capacity. However, compared to the

ESTIMATED SUPPLY (MILLION BARRELS/DAY)

Figure – Oil Dependency by Country

Source – Based on data reported by Reuters

Illustration: Tanvir/Econology/

previous year, by 2025, coal and gas-based energy production also increased by nearly 93 GW (75% rise). Even though it is at a far lower rate compared to the renewable sources-based energy production growth, it is still significant enough to show that their reliance on them is less likely to die in the near future. Non-fossil-fuel-based energy production often depends on the natural environment for electricity generation. Which, in the long run, is sustainable, but often in the short-run scenario can cause some disruption.

As they depend on the natural environment or its phenomena, a change of which can be pretty unpredictable or unavoidable, inconsistency in energy production can arise. For modern economic activities, inconsistency can drive the opportunity cost higher. So, to minimize this unpredictability, fossil-fuel-based energy generation is still necessary. Thus, the coal and gas-based power plants are still

entering into service, playing a crucial role in stabilizing the energy supply. The spatial inequality is also significant enough for energy production and demand. The northwestern and western provinces (like Xinjiang, Tibet, Inner Mongolia, etc.) produce the most renewable energy. But in those regions, demand is also low. On the other hand, the energy demand is higher in Eastern and Southern provinces (like Guangdong, Jiangsu, Shanghai, etc.).

Thus, the electricity produced in the northwest and western provinces needs to be transmitted by Ultra-High Voltage (UHV) lines, leading to higher energy wastage due to curtailment in those resource-rich regions. Roughly 5-10% of the energy gets curtailed during the process of transmission.

Thus, the problem is not really with the energy production, but rather it has something to do with allocation inefficiency.

Recent crises and non-renewable fuel problem

In 2025, China's crude oil import from Malaysia was around 1 million barrel per day. But Malaysia produced 650,000 barrel per day in that year. This discrepancy reflects its role as a transit hub for re-exported crude oil, including from some sanctioned nations.

As a neighboring country, Russia remains the largest supplier so far, with 2.04 million barrels per day supplied in the 2025 estimate. These sanctioned fuels were always cheaper for the country, often by \$5 to \$13 per barrel below Brent. However, everything changed on January 3 of 2026, when President Nicolás Maduro and his wife were abducted and imprisoned by the United States under 'narco-terrorism' and trafficking allegations. Supply from one of the largest crude oil suppliers of China, from whom they imported an average of approximately 470,000 barrels of crude oil per day, had become uncertain.

Things didn't turn better, as the U.S.-Iran conflict escalated into a war-like scenario. Iran, being an even bigger supplier of China's oil, exporting over 80% of shipments (approximately 1.38 million barrels per day), was struck by the conflict against the U.S. and Israel.

But, luckily for China, unlike the Venezuelan situation, Iran continued to maintain their supply even with the escalating geopolitical tensions, thanks to their control over the Strait of Hormuz. wDespite this relative relief, however, China is constantly reminded of its structural vulnerabilities within its energy security framework. Once, purchasing the discounted oil from

the sanctioned economies was a crucial strategy for the country. But recent troubles show it is time to think otherwise; this strategy comes with a major geopolitical liability.

Policy response analysis

According to the 2025 data by EMBER, 55% of the total energy production in China is still dependent on Coal. While contrary to this, a total of 430 GW of new solar and wind-powered renewable energy generating facility installation does show its strong will for renewable transition in the long run.

So, the strategy seems to be that non-renewable-based energy generation (like coal or gas) is assigned for fulfilling their short-run increasing energy demand while the renewable-based energy production facilities take over in the long-run. This renewable-based transition, however, is not only for lifting the image. This strategy can definitely fight the vulnerability of the country's dependency on foreign fuel imports. The recent crises in both South America and the Middle East show it clearly.

The electrification and strategic stockpiling of fuel are set to fight the foreign fuel dependency problem. And renewable energy is certainly a golden opportunity for the world's second largest populus nation to solve its biggest weakness to become a powerhouse of the world's economy. In addition to this, recently, China has also declared nearly 4 billion Yuan worth of investment in grid investment from 2026 to 2030 to combat the curtailing problem of the western and north-western provinces, cutting a large portion of the energy during

distribution. This project aims to solve the allocation inefficiency problem plaguing the country's energy infrastructure regarding the renewable energy transition.

Workers at the crossroads: Labour and the politics of Nigeria's energy transition

Rasaq Bello, Nigeria

Researcher at Michael Imoudu National Institute for Labour Studies

Picture: Collected

Nigeria's ambition to reach net-zero emissions by 2060 rests on an economy still powered by oil. The petroleum industry provides most of the country's export revenue and sustains millions of formal and informal livelihoods.

Yet, as global climate goals tighten and investment patterns shift, the future of these workers grows uncertain. The energy transition, celebrated in policy circles as a pathway to sustainability, carries deeper questions for those whose incomes and communities depend on fossil fuels.

Can Nigeria move toward cleaner energy without leaving its workers behind? The debate is no longer theoretical. With the launch of the Energy Transition Plan in 2022 and growing pressure from international

partners, the government has begun to reframe its development agenda around renewable energy (Federal Government of Nigeria, 2022). But labour voices remain faint in this process. For Nigeria's trade unions especially the National Union of Petroleum and Natural Gas Workers (NUPENG) and the Petroleum and Natural Gas Senior Staff Association of Nigeria (PENGASSAN) the transition cannot be "just" if it excludes the very people who built the energy economy.

Nigeria's energy transition in context

Nigeria is Africa's largest oil producer and one of its most carbon-intensive economies. Oil accounts for about 90 percent of foreign exchange earnings and more than

half of government revenue (World Bank, 2024). The national Energy Transition Plan outlines a gradual shift from fossil fuels toward renewables such as solar, hydro, and bioenergy. It projects a cost of roughly 1.9 trillion U.S. dollars by 2060 and identifies clean energy investments as essential to growth and energy access.

Despite the optimism, progress remains slow. Power generation capacity is still under 5,000 megawatts for a population exceeding 200 million (IRENA, 2023). The renewable energy sector contributes less than 10 percent of total electricity supply. Job creation within green industries is minimal, and most initiatives rely on donor support.

For a country grappling with mass unemployment, this limited transition risks widening inequality unless it deliberately incorporates social and labour concerns.

The wider context also matters. Nigeria's energy reforms are influenced by external financing conditions and international climate negotiations. Donors and investors often prioritise technological solutions and carbon metrics over human development needs (UNDP, 2023). The tension between global decarbonisation targets and local livelihoods is therefore acute. Without domestic policies that centre workers, the transition may replicate older patterns of exclusion.

Labour's position and concerns

For decades, Nigeria's oil unions have been central to industrial relations and national policy debates. NUPENG represents thousands of blue-collar oil and gas workers, while PENGASSAN organises senior and professional staff. Both unions

see the energy transition as inevitable but worry about its social consequences. Their concerns fall into three main areas. First, job security: as oil investments decline, the risk of redundancy grows. Recent divestments by major oil companies have already led to retrenchments and uncertainty. Second, informalisation: new energy jobs, where they exist, tend to be precarious and poorly regulated (ILO, 2022). Third, exclusion: the design of climate and energy policy rarely involves trade unions, despite their technical knowledge and industrial experience.

NUPENG has been particularly vocal about retraining and skills diversification.

Through its Green Hub initiative, it has begun exploring renewable energy training for young workers and community members in the Niger Delta (NUPENG, 2023). The union argues that local participation in new energy projects is essential for sustainability and peace building. PENGASSAN, for its part, has urged the federal government to include labour representatives in transition councils and decision-making bodies (PENGASSAN, 2024).

Both unions share the view that climate policy should not become another top-down reform imposed without social dialogue. However, challenges persist. Many union members remain skeptical of climate narratives they associate with Western pressure or elite interests.

Others doubt the government's capacity to implement large-scale retraining programmes. Without transparent communication and clear benefits, the idea of a just transition risks being dismissed as rhetorical.

The Politics of a “just” transition

The phrase “just transition” entered Nigeria’s policy vocabulary through international labour networks and climate advocacy groups.

Yet its meaning remains contested. In practice, government officials often interpret it narrowly—as a technical adjustment involving renewable energy investment and environmental regulation. For trade unions and social advocates, it should mean something broader: a negotiated transformation of the economy that ensures workers, communities, and regions dependent on fossil fuels are not left behind (Okafor & Adesina, 2022).

Three political factors complicate this vision.

First, the institutional framework for dialogue is weak. Labour–environment coordination is fragmented across ministries and agencies. There is no national platform where unions, employers, and civil society can jointly shape transition policies.

Second, climate governance in Nigeria is heavily donor-driven. International partners provide funding and expertise, but their priorities can overshadow domestic social concerns (African Development Bank, 2023). This dynamic often limits the space for independent labour input.

Third, existing industrial policies favor capital-intensive projects with limited employment impact. The green transition, unless reoriented, could reproduce this pattern replacing one form of exclusion with another.

A “just” transition therefore requires more than renewable energy investment. It demands governance reforms that give workers a voice in defining what the transition should look like. Without such participation, the process risks becoming another phase of structural adjustment modernization without social justice.

Emerging openings and opportunities

Despite the challenges, new possibilities are emerging.

The NUPENG Green Hub has trained small cohorts of workers and youths in solar installation and waste management. Some state governments are experimenting with renewable energy cooperatives that could integrate local labour.

A few universities and research institutes are developing curricula on energy transition and just transition principles, often in collaboration with labour institutions (Federal Ministry of Environment, 2023).

These early steps show that inclusive transition is achievable when workers are treated as partners, not bystanders. Unions can play an important role in monitoring climate spending, promoting decent work in green sectors, and linking job creation to environmental protection.

Equally important is the framing of climate action as a labour right the right to safe, sustainable, and dignified work in a changing environment. This perspective shifts the conversation from sacrifice to opportunity. It places the worker at the centre of policy, where sustainability becomes not only an ecological goal but also a social contract.

Conclusion

Nigeria's path to net-zero will test its political and institutional capacity. The transition to clean energy must balance environmental ambition with economic and social realities. For millions of workers tied to the oil economy, the question is not whether change will come, but how fairly it will be managed. A just transition is not a slogan; it is a commitment to equity. It calls for dialogue between government, employers, and unions; for investments in skills and local industries; and for policies that protect workers through the transformation ahead. Nigeria's energy future can be both green and just but only if workers remain at the heart of the transition.

The country's green transition will succeed not when the last oil well shuts down, but when the workers who powered it find a place in the new energy economy.

Author bio: Rasaan Bello is a researcher at the Michael Imoudu National Institute for Labour Studies, Nigeria, and an alumnus of the Global Labour University, Germany. His work focuses on just transition, climate justice, labour–environmental governance, and platform Precarity.

Comparative development trajectories Singapore and Bangladesh

Md. Yasin Arafat

Illustration: AI generated

Singapore and Bangladesh are often placed in the same broad category: post-colonial Asian economies that pursued export-led growth. Yet core development indicators reveal a stark divergence.

The World Bank's GDP per capita series for 2024 reports about \$90,674 for Singapore and about \$2,593 for Bangladesh. The UNDP Human Development Report 2023/24 places Singapore's HDI at 0.946 (very high) and Bangladesh's at 0.685 (medium). Governance outcomes differ sharply as well: Transparency International's Corruption Perceptions Index 2024 scores Singapore at 84 (rank 3) and Bangladesh at 23 (rank 151).

Starting points and policy sequencing

Singapore's early challenge was not poverty on the scale of Bangladesh, but survival in a small, resource-poor city-state after separation from Malaysia in 1965. Its response was a tightly coordinated

development strategy: export-oriented industrialisation, aggressive investment promotion, and rapid infrastructure build-out.

Chia's review of the 'Singapore model' highlights how industrial policy evolved from labour-intensive manufacturing toward higher-value activities as wages rose.

Bangladesh entered independence in 1971 after war damage and deep rural poverty. Early policy leaned toward state-led, agro-based import substitution, and progress was repeatedly interrupted by political turbulence and administrative weakness.

From the 1980s, trade liberalisation and export processing zones helped shift the economy toward export-led growth. Brookings contributor A. Mahmood links pragmatic policy steps - including rural connectivity and support for the ready-made garment sector - to poverty reduction

in the 2010s.

Institutions: State capacity versus political volatility

The central contrast is not simply ‘markets versus state’ but the quality and credibility of the state. Singapore’s long-run policy continuity and meritocratic bureaucracy made it easier to coordinate land use, housing, skills, and industrial upgrading. Low perceived corruption is consistent with that institutional story: Transparency International’s CPI 2024 places Singapore among the world’s cleanest administrations.

Bangladesh’s institutions have delivered important social gains, but governance remains a binding constraint for structural transformation. The same CPI report rates Bangladesh far lower, and the World Bank’s inequality series (Gini = 0.309 in 2022) signals persistent distributional pressure. For investors, regulatory

delays, politicisation, and weak contract enforcement can matter as much as wages or tax incentives - raising the ‘hidden tax’ on investment.

Bangladesh’s growth has been impressive and poverty fell sharply in the 2010s; the paper’s summary notes estimates of roughly 25 million people lifted out of poverty since 2010. However, export concentration remains high: ready-made garments are described as roughly four-fifths of merchandise exports, leaving the economy exposed to sector-specific shocks and limited learning spillovers.

Singapore, by contrast, treated industrial upgrading as a moving target. As labour-intensive activities matured, policy shifted toward electronics, logistics, finance, and other skill-intensive services, supported by deliberate investment in workforce training and continuous attraction of high-quality FDI.

Human development: Progress with different ceilings

Bangladesh's 'human development puzzle' is real: literacy and health improved rapidly despite low public spending shares. The World Bank literacy series puts adult literacy at 76.36% in 2021, and life expectancy reached 74.4 years in 2023. These gains were reinforced by NGO delivery models, female education gains, and targeted social programmes.

Singapore sits near the global frontier: adult literacy is reported at 97.65% and life expectancy at 82.9 years. In a high-income setting, the constraint is less basic access and more the distribution of opportunity and the cost of living. Even so, universal public housing and compulsory savings have historically limited extreme deprivation.

Sustainability under asymmetric risks

Development paths are increasingly shaped by climate constraints. UN sources cited in the paper warn that around 17% of Bangladesh's land area could be submerged by 2050, with large implications for cropland and displacement. Bangladesh has responded with adaptation investments - cyclone shelters, climate-resilient crops, and community innovations such as floating gardens - but financing and implementation capacity limit scale.

Singapore's sustainability problem is different: land scarcity and energy dependence. Climate Action Tracker's country profile notes goals under the Singapore Green Plan 2030, and the paper reports a rapid scale-up of solar capacity from 15 MW (2013) to about 1.17 GW

(2023), alongside plans to import electricity through regional grids.

What Bangladesh can borrow and what it cannot

Singapore's experience does not offer a plug-and-play blueprint. Bangladesh is larger, poorer, and politically more pluralistic. Yet the comparison is still useful if framed as a question of state capability and economic complexity.

Policy takeaways for Bangladesh

Make policy credibility a competitiveness strategy: regulatory predictability, professional bureaucracy, and anti-corruption enforcement reduce the hidden tax on investment.

Push export diversification beyond garments by linking industrial policy to skills, logistics, and technology diffusion - not just tax holidays.

Treat cities as productivity platforms: faster, greener urban infrastructure is essential as urbanisation rises.

Scale climate adaptation with durable financing and local implementation capacity, because climate risk is already a growth constraint.

About Author

Arafat, a UNDP FutureNation Volunteer, is a student of Development Economics interested in inequality, policy design, and the political economy of development. His writing sits at the intersection of research and public discourse, where data meets narrative and economics speaks to lived experience.
yasinibnsiddik@gmail.com

Procedural efficiency and the green transition: A new era for the judicial system

Adv. Tirtha Ghosh . LL.B. (Hon's). Stamford University Bangladesh

Photo: Collected

As of now, we cannot think of our judicial system to be paperless. Though we are living in an era of technological breakthrough. AI is taking over our everyday life. But our judicial system is still living in the 17th century. It has adapted few things here and there, but there is still a hundred miles to go. It is estimated that approximately 13 to 26 million trees are cut down every day worldwide to produce paper, with a middle-of-the-road estimate around 19 million.

On average, one standard mature tree (such as pine or similar pulpwood) can produce approximately 10,000 to 20,000 sheets of paper. An average pulp tree is considered to be around 45 feet tall with an 8-inch diameter. Heavier (higher GSM) or coated paper requires more wood, reducing the number of sheets per tree. Such as Stamp papers and Cartridge papers as they are high-quality, thick, and durable paper with a slightly textured surface.

The most immediate effect of cutting trees for paper is deforestation. Forests are home to a vast range of plant and animal species. When trees are removed, these habitats are destroyed, forcing wildlife to relocate or perish. Over time, this leads to a decline in biodiversity and disrupts entire ecosystems. It doesn't take a genius to understand its' consequences.

Where, even before filing a suit, we need documents to know what the actual issues are. When a party(plaintiff) wants to file a suit, the first thing he/they need(s) is to hire an advocate by signing a Wakalatnama. Here starts the journey of the use of papers which is essential. The plaintiff(s) will tell their part of the truth in the 'Plaint'. The plaintiff mustn't be written on any regular paper. It has to be stamp papers to pay the court fees. And the plaintiff(s) also have to submit all the necessary documents to support their claims. The plaintiff may consist of 10 paper or maybe 20 or 50 depending

on the facts and claims of the plaintiff(s).

After the submission of the plaint as well as necessary documents, the court shall record the suit and provide a suit number. Then the opponent party(defendant) needs to be notified that they have been sued. So the court will serve summons to the defendant(s). Each summons would require having a copy of the plaint. If there are multiple defendants, the plaintiff(s) must provide each defendant with a copy of summon along with a copy of plaint as well. Here, the number of papers is multiplied by the number of defendants. Already we lost track of the number of papers needed to file a single suit. And we still haven't heard the defendants' story.

Now the defendant(s) would submit 'Written Statement' which is their side of the truth, within 30 working days after receiving the summon. And each plaintiff needs a copy of that written statement to know what and how they are denying or accepting (if any) the points of their claim.

As of now, the same plaint or written statement is being copied multiple times just for a single suit. And the suit has not even reached to the main proceedings. So much paper is already being used in one suit. There are so many pending suits and new ones are being filed every day.

In a news article from The Financial Express in 2025 named "Apex court heaving under logjam of half-million cases" says, "Between 2015 and 2024, more than 849,000 cases were filed in the High Court Division and over 95,000 in the Appellate Division of the Supreme Court, while the number of disposals fell short to cope with the pressure, leaving hundreds of thousands of cases pending for years.

By the end of 2023, nearly 4.3 million cases had remained pending across all courts, with the bulk in district-level courts, according to sources close to the judiciary. Of the total, 26,517 cases were pending with the Appellate Division, 543,847 with the High Court Division, and 3,729,235 in the district-level courts."¹

Considering all the stats of the old cases pending and new ones being filed every day, how many sheets of paper are being used in total in the whole judicial system? And what's happening to the papers of the cases which are being resolved? Are they being recycled?

What if it's possible to reduce the excessive use of paper? And there is no alternative to digitalization. The government can introduce servers to each District Courts of the Judicial System to store digital copies of the pending suits/cases which are on trial at the moment as well as submit new ones directly on to the server. The plaint would need to be submitted on the format of the server of the judicial system along with supporting documents. The wakalathnama can be left as it is, as it requires seal, signature and stamp.

After submitting the plaint, it cannot be amended without the authorization or the permission of the presiding judge. Also, the required court fees which would be collected via online payment gateway while submitting the plaint. Thus, the plaint(stamp papers) is no longer needed. Here, we've already saved some papers.

1 <https://today.thefinancialexpress.com.bd/first-page/apex-court-heaving-under-logjam-of-half-million-cases-1761761134>

The next step would be to issue the summons to the defendants. Now the courts don't have to send physical copies of the plaint to each defendant as the copy of the plaint and all the necessary documents already exist on the server. The court may send only one piece of paper bearing the name and seal of the court, sign of the presiding judge and brief details of the nature of the suit, the suit number and instructions to find the plaint on the judicial system website/server. The defendant(s) can also submit their written statement in the same manner. Thus, we can kill two birds with one stone.

Anyone who has ever faced the court once in his lifetime is fed up with the lengthy process of the judicial system. In this way, the process time also gets shorter and easier as well as saving a lot of papers just by sending one piece of paper as a summons other than sending each defendant a copy of the plaint along with the summons.

Nowadays khatiyans and mouza maps, land tax payment etc. are being recorded online. The required documents for the disputed property or criminal records which already exist on the Govt. server don't need to be provided by the parties manually to the trial court. The parties may pay the necessary fees to the court and the court itself, having authority, may get the relevant documents online for every suit/case on trial. Thus, the proceeding time is being utilized properly. And the usage of the papers is also being shortened.

Though this also raises the concern of security and privacy. Because bringing all the documents under one roof is risky as it may get to the wrong hands or being locked out of access to it. The servers should

be decentralized and have strong secure encryption. And other necessary measures should be considered. The Supreme Court would have access to all the subordinate courts' servers. So that, at the time of appeal, the parties don't have to collect any of the copy of the plaints, exhibits, copy of the decree or orders passed by the subordinate court. After all the processes are complete then the parties may ask for the certified hardcopy of the judgement, decree or order from the court.

It is high time the Supreme Court Secretariat took action to reduce the use of paper on the court premises and fully digitalize the judicial system. It's not possible to make changes overnight but it's indispensable to speed up the judicial processes and save the hassle of a long perishing trial by the meantime saving the environment by reducing the demand of paper.

About Author

Adv. Tirtha Ghosh is a lawyer committed to advancing the standards of the legal profession by maintaining a transparent and equitable court environment for all. His goal is to combine rigorous legal advocacy with a vision for a more efficient and accessible judicial system. He can be reached at: tirtha2826@gmail.com

You vs You: The conflict between your condition and your choice

Muhammad Tanvir Ahmmed

Art: 'The Double Secret' by René Magritte

Why does a person, even after realizing a habit is harmful, keep returning to it as if something deeper is pulling the strings? And more importantly, is this struggle a fight against something within us... or something built around us?

These questions point toward a quiet but powerful conflict, 'You vs You.' Not a battle of strength, but a conflict between what has shaped you and what you choose to become. Every person carries an invisible blueprint within them, their genes. These genes shape our physical traits, influence our temperament, and even affect how we respond to stress, pleasure, and risk. At first glance, it often feels like some habits are

“born with us.” A person may struggle with anger, impulsiveness, addiction, or lack of discipline from an early age, creating the illusion that these behaviors are inherited and fixed.

Scientific research in Behavioral Genetics supports the idea that we can inherit certain tendencies, such as emotional reactivity or risk-taking behavior. But tendencies are not destiny. If biology alone defined us, change would be impossible. Yet, change happens every day. The real story lies in how these tendencies interact with our environment. From childhood, we are shaped by our surroundings, especially our families. Through Social Learning Theory,

introduced by Albert Bandura, we learn by observing and imitating those closest to us. If a child grows up in an environment where unhealthy habits are normalized, those behaviors often become part of their daily life.

Over time, repetition turns actions into patterns, and patterns into identity. What feels like “who you are” is often a reflection of what you have repeatedly done. This is where the conflict begins. Because what you call “yourself” is often a mix of inherited tendencies and learned behaviors, your conditioning. And yet, within that structure, there exists something powerful: awareness, the ability to pause, reflect, and choose differently.

Modern science strengthens this idea rather than weakening it. The concept of Epigenetics shows that genes are not fixed commands; they can be activated or suppressed depending on the environment and lifestyle. In other words, your surroundings and choices influence how your biology expresses itself.

Even more powerful is Neuroplasticity, the brain’s ability to rewire itself. Every repeated action strengthens certain neural pathways, making behaviors automatic. But this process works both ways. New actions, repeated consistently, can weaken old patterns and build new ones.

So the habits that feel “like you” are, in many ways, the result of loops your brain has practiced over time. This is where ideas from Atomic Habits by James Clear bring clarity. Clear argues that behavior is not simply a matter of willpower, but of systems. What we repeatedly do is shaped

by cues, environment, and rewards, a continuous cycle that reinforces itself. The problem is rarely the person; it is the system surrounding them.

This aligns perfectly with the idea of conditioning. You don’t just inherit tendencies, you grow inside systems that make certain behaviors easy and others difficult. But then comes the role of choice. Choice is not a single moment of decision. It is a process of redesign, changing environments, interrupting patterns, and building new systems. It is slow, often uncomfortable, and rarely visible at first. That is why the conflict feels so personal. It is not just about changing what you do, but about challenging what you have become used to being. This is the essence of “You vs You.”

Not a fight against your genes, but against unconscious patterns. Not a rejection of your past, but a redefinition of your future. Breaking a bad habit is never easy. When a behavior is reinforced both by internal tendencies and external environment, overcoming it requires conscious resistance.

It demands self-awareness, consistency, and often a change in surroundings. This is why some people feel like they are constantly “fighting themselves.” In reality, they are challenging patterns that have been built over years of repetition and reinforcement. Yet, this struggle is also what defines human growth. The ability to reflect, to resist, and to change is uniquely human. While your genes may whisper certain tendencies, your choices determine whether you listen or not. In the end, the phrase “You vs You” holds a deeper truth. The battle is not against your genes, but against the

unconscious version of yourself shaped by habit and environment. And the victory does not come from denying your nature, but from understanding it and choosing, again and again, who you want to become. You may not have chosen the habits you carry. But the decision to continue them or to change them always is. And that is where the real power lies.

About Author

Muhammad Tanvir Ahmmed is Communications Associate at Econology. He can be reached at: its0tanvir@gmail.com

How a Ghanaian scientist is rethinking drug research with AI

Afia Agyapomaa Ofosu . Science Journalist

Dr. Adi-Dako Explains Chip Technology

“Pharmacist, I have a prescription from my local clinic. The drug was unavailable there, so I had to get it elsewhere.”

It is a familiar exchange in many pharmacies across Ghana. A patient arrives with a prescription, hoping the medicine will be in stock. Few think about the long path that medicine travelled before reaching the shelf — the repeated experiments, the

waiting, the validation. Fewer still imagine how that path is beginning to change with artificial intelligence.

A Chip in Her Palm

Inside the AI in pharmaceutical discovery lab at Imperial College London’s White City Campus, Dr Ofosua Klozie Adi-Dako holds out something small and transparent. “It looks simple,” she says, passing it around, “but this is where the experiments

are now.”

The object resting on her palm is a thin, clear chip. It hardly resembles a place for serious scientific work. Yet this is where she now runs tests that once demanded long hours and repeated trials.

Rethinking the lab

Dr Adi-Dako is a lecturer at the Department of Pharmacy at the University of Ghana and a Schmidt Global Faculty Fellow. For years, she worked within the familiar rhythm of laboratory research. “You run one experiment.

If it doesn’t go well, you repeat it. Sometimes, when you are tracking what happens in certain conditions, you have to sit throughout the night to monitor it. After that, you still move to animal models to validate what you’ve done in the lab. That’s the traditional way.” She explains that meeting research demands in a short time often requires many hands and extended periods of work.

“If you look at this critically, you may need about ten scientists working for a long time to meet the demand for results.”

The chip introduces a different pace.

She designed it herself using Autodesk software before it was laser-cut into shape from a special plastic. Within it are tiny channels where droplets measured in nanolitres and picolitres move through micro-pathways.

“With this chip, I can run many experiments at the same time, instead of doing one experiment manually and repeating it for weeks.”

Inside the drug discovery lab

Inside the chip, she recreates what happens in the human intestine.

“What we’re doing is mimicking what happens in the intestine. We create an artificial membrane and watch how a drug moves through it.”

Before a medicine can treat disease, it must cross body membranes for absorption. On the chip, a drug is placed on one side of a delicate barrier. She then observes how it permeates through to the other side.

“Permeability is very important. If a drug cannot pass through membranes properly, then you don’t have treatment. And if the movement is inconsistent, that affects the outcome.” Under a microscope, the setup reveals droplets in a liquid environment, separated by an artificial layer that behaves like a membrane. This is only one well. The full chip contains many wells, each running its own test.

“The setup is able to generate over a thousand data points within a very short time. Compared to the traditional approach, this would take many months.”

Handling the chip requires precision. She has trained herself to pipette carefully so droplets do not fuse, fragment, or disturb the delicate layer between them.

Where AI comes in

The large volume of data produced by the chip is analysed using artificial intelligence. “Normally, within human capacity, we analyse data as we see it. But the AI model is able to detect anomalies and analyse patterns from different angles that I would

not see traditionally. It unravels complex data patterns and gives us much more information.”

These insights guide the next stages of drug development and reduce the number of animal experiments needed for validation. Since arriving in London in September 2025, she has trained with researchers at the I-X Center for AI in Science, working with programmers and other researchers to refine her modelling skills.

“This is a network science approach to finding solutions in healthcare,” she says. “It’s a unique opportunity to enhance my skill.”

Bringing it home

The work is not meant to remain in London. As part of her fellowship, she is developing a system she will carry back to Ghana. The same experiments she runs here will be possible in her lab in Accra, with continued collaboration after she returns.

“It’s going to have faster solutions. AI can predict what will happen, even with compounds you haven’t worked with before. It can also extend to the natural compounds that we have in Ghana.” For researchers at home, this means earlier answers about which compounds are worth pursuing before entering expensive stages of testing.

She sums it up simply: “It’s cost-effective, accurate, and it brings speed.”

When she returns to the University of Ghana, the small chip will sit quietly on a lab bench. Yet it will be doing work that once required long hours, repeated trials, and many hands — producing results in days instead of months, and changing how

drug research is approached.

This report is part of the UK-Ghana ST&I Media Training Programme.

The writer is a science journalist.

E-mail: prissyof@yahoo.com

Designing the right incentives to foster environmental literacy in society

Indranil Deb | *expandnext* | *Environment Management 2024, IISc, Bengaluru*

Environmental literacy¹ is an individual's understanding of how our local environments and the world at large are affected by the way we obtain resources. It is important for individuals, especially students to realize that our resources are depletable and our efforts to obtain those resources affect our environment on a global scale. Understanding the natural environment and the impact human activity has on it is essential to making informed decisions that affect the environment and human health now and in the future.

Environmental literacy was first used by Roth in 1968. According to Roth's definition, the ones who have fundamental knowledge about their environment are called as environmental literate (Roth, 1968). Environmental literacy consists of some behaviors such as comprehending of environment, having environmental knowledge and skills, displaying environmental attitudes. Moreover, it provides the people with a long lasting and sustainable relationship with the areas they live in (McBride et al., 2013; Roth, 2002). Environmental literacy refers to an individual's understanding, skills and motivation to make responsible decisions that consider his or her relationships with natural systems, communities and future generations (Fang, Hassan and LePage, 2023). How can we create meaningful

1 Environmental Literacy: A Lot More than the 3 Rs | Savvas

opportunities for students, professionals, individuals, etc to learn about the world around them and inspire a sense of personal and collective responsibility

One adaptable tool is the Environmental Literacy Ladder (Fig1), developed by the Campaign for Environmental Literacy. This model defines five essential components of environmental literacy: Awareness, Knowledge, Attitudes, Skills, and Action. Structured as a loose hierarchy, it moves

from basic to more advanced elements, with each step building on the previous one. These overlap often in real life scenarios. Most importantly, achieving environmental literacy requires all levels of the ladder; addressing any one component alone won't achieve true literacy!

Building on the above viewpoints, this article seeks to propose a few approaches or ideas that may help nudge human behavior towards greater environmental literacy. They are:

Green environment loyalty program

This program rewards a company, institutions, schools that runs to promote eco-friendly behaviors and practices. While it sounds transactional but at the basic levels such as in schools – there must be rewards to implement the smallest of ideas into action to safeguard the mother earth and its diversity. The student or groups of students must be rewarded in terms of marks or certification that adds to their character and future work prospects. This delta shift in action would eventually turn out to be mindset and lifestyle in next decade or few years. Continuous persuasion is the key here. Backed by government policy and regulations.

To push environmental literacy via Loyalty program in the commercial space is to overcome one of the biggest challenges is balancing two types of loyalty: transactional and emotional. Eco-linked Tax rebates in Property for both home buyers and real estate developers. Currently there are tax benefits under solar energy systems/ panels, rainwater harvesting and waste disposal management in different states in India. However, these initiatives

are availed by middle or upper middle sections of society who are ready to invest initially to get tax rebates or other attached benefits including creating eco friendly practice.

To create wider awareness among home buyers and developers, industry should bring few major policy changes with legal impacts (for not following). These policies are tax linked rebate such buying homes from real estate brands which follow environmentally friendly design not for sake of it but follow anti encroachment culture just to pocket huge profits or do not bend the system using power or other negotiable practices. These tax benefits are extended to home builders and developers as well as consumers of real estate of all size and forms. At the same time laws should be introduced that restricts developers from any forms of encroachments which impact directly or indirectly the nature or disrupt ecological balance in short or long term.

Social media algorithms for all forms of environment-friendly contents

To encourage organic views (in millions or billions) on different social media, specially by individual environmental or eco enthusiast – popular social media platforms such as reels, fb, LinkedIn, etc must introduce algorithms that would help such content easily visible to the mass. These contents should free to publish with exclusive wider reach so that environmental literacy is achieved fast and should not be found or discovered via social media searches and key words. People are attuned to more than just social signals, they also notice the actions of people around them (social proof, as discussed above). The more

often we see a particular behavior, the more it becomes “normal” and we internalize it as a norm. Think Fashion – the first time we see a “new look” it might look absurd but soon it becomes normal. Similarly, the more we consume green content the more we will internalise into action and lifestyle.

DO YOU HAVE STORIES TO TELL?

SEND US YOUR ARTICLES AND WRITINGS HERE:

 hq.econology@gmail.com

The silent revolution: How Bangladesh's garment giants are fighting for a green future

Md. Shawon Gazi

Picture: Collected

In the dystopian industrial centers of Savar and Gazipur, the sewing needles have always beat the rhythm of the Bangladesh economy and it is the story of miraculous growth as the ready-made garment (RMG) business grew to be more than 81 percent of the export income of the country and provides jobs to millions of women and changes the social and economic fabric of the nation.

However, this success story is at a critical crossroad in Bangladesh, as it is on the verge of leaving the Least Developed Country (LDC) in November 2026. The 2023-24 fiscal year RMG exports were estimated at about \$36.15 billion, and it is expected to increase to about \$39.35 billion in the 2024-25 fiscal year mainly because of

preferential market access through the EU Everything But Arms (EBA) arrangement that allowed RMG a duty-free entry to European markets. The looming threat of loss of these trade privileges, as well as the increasing compliance cost of the European Green Deal, has now emerged as a real menace to the industry and now asks the burning question that whether the Bangladesh apparel sector can adjust to a greener, more competitive world of trade or not. The End of an Era: Bangladesh was receiving a 'golden ticket' in the world trade: Least Developed Country (LDC). This enabled its shirts and trousers to get into the huge European Union market without the payment of duties. However, Bangladesh will come out of this status in 2026. The triumph of economic maturity

Annual CO₂ emissions

Carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions from fossil fuels and industry¹. Land-use change emissions² are not included.

costs a lot with a possible tariff of 12% on exports that may drastically diminish its competitiveness factor.

To make matters more dramatic, a formidable rival has entered the arena. Vietnam, Bangladesh's main competitor, has already secured a free trade agreement (EVFTA) with the EU. Just as Bangladesh loses its privileges, Vietnam's tariffs are dropping to zero. This "dual trade preference erosion" threatens to divert significant trade away from Bangladesh, with models predicting a potential decline in apparel exports by nearly 20% in the face of this stiff competition.

The green wall

Tariffs are always half the battle. Another green wall is building up around Europe. The EU is not just in the market to find the cheapest price but they are also demanding the least carbon footprint. The laws like the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) are aimed at sanctioning so-called dirty imports and imposing a carbon price on them.

Though CBAM focuses at the beginning on such heavy industries as steel, cement, and aluminum. Its spillover effects are inevitable, and its spillover in other places accounts for about 45% of the total world industrial CO₂ emissions. More than three-quarters of European clothing brands

are now pushing carbon responsibility throughout the supply chain by obliging suppliers to report on emissions.

In the case of Bangladesh, the red flags are flying. The EU is the most significant market as it takes almost half of the entire Bangladesh apparel export, close to 50-55 percent. Other research organizations like SANEM have cautioned that the lack of adherence to the emerging Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) standards may cut the exports of Bangladesh to the European Union by up to 30%, which corresponds to a loss of USD 810 billion per year. The message of the West is quite clear: the times when one could just compete by lower labor costs are gone. The world has entered a new age; the age of green credentials, carbon transparency and climate compliance. port.

The Struggle for Solar

The desire to reform does exist in the factories of Bangladesh, which produce clothes. It already has the highest number of green manufacturing firms in the world, with 273 LEED-certified garment factories of which 115 have been Platinum-rated.

The largest concentration in the world. Over 60% of factory owners currently attribute the need to be eco-friendly as the central reason behind their transition to renewable energy. But ambition is now coming into a head with physics and finance. In case of most factories this is as far as the rooftop goes. A mere limitation that stands out is almost three-quarters of the owners who are willing to install solar have been blocked by lack of sufficient space to power up energy-intensive machinery on the roof. Cost is the impediment of smaller factories. Renewables are not an affordable luxury

due to high initial cost of installation unless the policy is supported. As a result, only about 31% of apparel factories have adopted renewable technologies and in most cases, these systems supply just 5–10% of total energy demand, leaving factories tied to an increasingly expensive national grid. The gap between green intent and green energy remains wide, and without structural solutions, good intentions alone will not decarbonize Bangladesh's factories.

Treasures in the Trash: However, there is some ray of hope concealed in the garbage bins. The textile wastes in Bangladesh are tremendous, and the wastes are locally referred to as “Jhut”. Presently, a black market is trapping this waste. This “trash” would be refrigerated and re-used to turn into billions of dollars in revenue. Recycled fibers are being demanded in the European market, the Man-Made Fibers (MMF) have taken over 70% of the entire world apparel market. Bangladesh would be able to give the same material that EU buyers are requesting by recycling plastic and fabric wasted materials. However, the high taxes and absence of policies to back this circular economy keep the latter rotating.

A Path Through the Storm

The industry is becoming imaginative, to come out of this perfect storm. As they are too small on the rooftops, they are turning to Corporate Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs). This would enable the factories to purchase green electricity produced by solar parks at a distance and do away with installations in the sites. Simultaneously, the industry is crying out for a champion. Surveyed factory owners overwhelmingly (91%) point to the government, asking for financial incentives and policy reforms to

SQ Group, a leading apparel manufacturer in Bangladesh, is renowned for its sustainability and operates multiple LEED Platinum-certified manufacturing facilities.

level the playing field.

The next chapter

The history of garment sector in Bangladesh is not complete yet. It is now composing a chapter on resilience. It is not merely about sewing clothes nowadays but sewing sustainability into the very fabric of the industry. Through renewable energy, unlocking waste potentials, and navigating the new, intricate world of green trade diplomacy, Bangladesh will be able to transform these headwinds into a tailwind that forces it into a great, middle-income country in the future.

Regional silence, human crisis: Rethinking refugee governance in South Asia

Tasnuva Tanzum . Development Studies (Masters) . BUP

Why, in a region so heavily interconnected by history, geography and shared challenges does refugee governance remain fragmented. The world has been going through an unprecedented displacement crisis for a long time.

As of mid-2025 almost 117.3 million people are forcibly displaced worldwide due to conflict, violence, political instability, climate related disaster. Ongoing war region such as Myanmar, Palestine, Ukraine, Sudan have significantly increased refugee flow across borders.

The refugee in the present time is arguably the worst since World War 2. In the dusty expanse of Cox’s Bazar, one of the largest refugee settlements stretches beyond the horizon, home to over a million Rohingya who escaped violence with the hope to survive. Their existence is not just humanitarian concern, it is a stark reminder

of a deeper regional shortcomings. Despite recurring displacement crisis across South Asia, a coordinated regional response remains largely absent. In a region bound by shared history, culture and borders South Asia remains deeply divided on one urgent issue, how to protect those forces to flee.

Global displacement framework:

Across the world, forced displacement is no longer an exception crisis, it is now a permanent feature of global politics. Millions of people move across borders each year due to war, persecution and environmental disasters yet the system designed to protect them still relies on framework that was built in the aftermath of World War 2.

At its core is the 1951 Refugee Convention and its 1967 Protocol, which define refugee

status and establish the principle of nonrefoulement, preventing nations from returning individual to danger. United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) created this architecture in 1950 to coordinate international protection, emergency assistance and durable solution such as voluntary repatriation, local integration or resettlement.

Unfortunately, this system is fundamentally dependent on state compliance. In reality this protection is uneven and highly political especially in region where states are not party to the convention but still hold large amount of refugee population.

South Asia: A region shaped by displacement

South Asia stands out as one of the most historically saturated displacement zones in the world. Force migration here is not episodic, it is structural.

From partition in 1947 to the 1971 Bangladesh Liberation War to Afghanistan's decade long conflict and Myanmar's Rohingya crisis, displacement has repeatedly reshaped this region political landscape.

Afghanistan remains a major source of refugees due to prolonged instability, with millions usually hosted in Pakistan and Iran. Bangladesh currently hosts over a million Rohingya refugees concentrated in Cox's Bazar.

India also has large history of hosting refugees from neighboring countries over time including Tibetans, Sri Lankan Tamils, Chakma, Afghans and Rohingya population.

Refugee populations in South Asia

Despite this long history of displacement, most South Asian states are not parties to the 1951 Refugee Convention. Therefore, refugee governance in these countries generally handled through domestic administrative system rather than legal obligations. This is why refugees protection in South Asia is inconsistent in long term. At the same time environmental pressure are adding new layer of complexity.

This regional refugee architecture gap is particularly striking because regional institution already exists. SAARC and BIMSTEC both bring countries together under formal framework. Yet neither of these institutions has developed a structured approach to refugee protection or displacement. Instead of that, migration is indirectly managed through security policies, bilateral diplomacy or development cooperation. This leaves a huge disconnection between global humanitarian norms and regional practices. SAARC, Ambition Constrained by Politics Established in 1985, SAARC was designed to promote regional cooperation in development and social progress. In reality, however, it's effectiveness in sensitive areas such as displacement has been very limited.

A key restriction is structural, the SAARC Charter discourage discussion of bilateral disputes even though many displacements crisis directly stem from such tensions, this makes collective actions extremely difficult. Political mistrust among member states has further weakened the organization, often leading to stalled summits and limited operational outcomes. There is currently no regional refugee framework under SAARC unlike other regional blocks. It

also lacks binding mechanism for asylum or protection for refugee population. Most member country rely on domestic policies while UNHCR plays a supplementary role. South Asian nations reluctance to adopt the 1951 Convention is often linked to concerns over sovereignty and security risk. Refugees are frequently referred to as a national security issue rather than a humanitarian responsibility which also limits prospects for regional cooperation. Still SAARC have potential. Its Social Charter and development intuitions could be expanded to incorporate displacement related issues.

BIMSTEC; emerging space with indirect relevance

BIMSTEC, formed in 1997, connects South and Southeast Asia around the Bay of Bengal and focuses primarily on economic and technical cooperation. Unlike SAARC, it includes making it relevant to the Rohingya crisis. Refugee Governance is not its formal mandate. Its consensus-based structure and development-oriented focus have kept it away from politically sensitive humanitarian issues. Yet BIMSTEC's rising attention to security cooperation provide indirect relevance to displacement issues particularly irregular migration.

Despite the regional impact of Rohingya crisis, it has not been formally addressed within BIMSTEC cause diplomatic sensitive. Analyst argues that countries like Bangladesh and India could potentially use BIMSTEC to align humanitarian coordination with economic cooperation, linking development incentives with stabilization efforts in Myanmar's Rakhine State. Across both SAARC and BIMSTEC, several structural constraints persist.

Sovereignty concerns remain dominant, with nations prioritize domestic stability over regional humanitarian situation. Geopolitical tension among neighboring countries further complicate cooperation, as many displacement crises originate from interstate conflicts. Institutional weakness is another barrier, as neither has enforcement capacity or binding legal instruments. At the same time, burden-sharing is heavily unequal with frontline state like Pakistan and Bangladesh hosting large refugee population without regional support mechanism. Refugee governance is a complicated issue in South Asia because of political tensions and weak coordination among states. Regional organization such SAARC and BIMSTEC has limited effectiveness due to disagreements and consensus-based system which restricts action on sensitive issues like refugee movement. Among these BIMSTEC appears to be more promising since it focuses on economic, technical and emerging security cooperation which could support displacement management. It seems that overall, the progress is more likely to be gradual rather than through major institutional change. Small steps such as improving humanitarian condition, sharing data and encouraging sub-regional cooperation many slowly build trust and allow refugee issues to be included within broader development actions.

About Author

Tasnuva Tanzum is a student of Environmental and Resource Economics with a strong academic interest in environmental sustainability And development. she has experience in research focused on global development and environmental issues. She aims to build expertise in international policy and sustainable development.

